

**Architectural and structural design of the Tianjin
Hongqiao middle school teaching building in Hongqiao
district, Tianjin city**

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Original statement

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ABSTRACT OF DESIGN

This report is about the calculation of the Tianjin Hongqiao middle school teaching building in Hongqiao district, Tianjin city.

The architecture design includes architectural scheme design, the design of architecture finishes and the plane, elevation and section design of the building.

This design implements the design principle of "practical, safe, economical and aesthetically impressive". In accordance with the architectural design specifications, the factors affecting the design should be carefully considered according to the relationship between the structure and the overall details of the building.

The structural design consists of two parts: the computerized part using YJK Structural analytic software and the hand-calculated part. The results obtained from the YJK software were adjusted and re-calculated iteratively until the building structure meets the safety requirements such as the earthquake-resistance requirements, and the last adjustment is applied for hand-calculated part. The hand-calculated part consists of the section size calculations, distribution and dead load. Architectural drawings were completed through AutoCAD while the construction drawings were completed through the YJK software.

In the design process, the whole structure strictly follows the requirements of relevant specialties and norms, refers to relevant materials and relevant national norms, and comprehensively and scientifically considers all aspects of the design requirements. In a word, the principle of this design is applicable, safe, economical and usable. Reasonable design of building structure is an important basis for site construction.

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CHAPTER 1 DESIGN RESOURCES

1.1 (Project Overview)

1.1.1 Project name

Architectural & Structural design of the Tianjin Hongqiao middle school teaching building.

1.1.2 Construction Place

The project is located in Hongqiao district, Tianjin city.

1.1.3 Project Introduction

The project is an Architectural and Structural design of a 5-storey middle school teaching building. It is a Reinforced Concrete frame structure. The building structure has 16 spans in the longitudinal direction with each span length 4.5m and 3 spans in the transversal direction of 6.9m+2.4m+6.9m. The structure has 5 storeys. All the floors from the first to the fifth are 3.6 meters high each. The indoor and outdoor height difference is 0.45 meters. The total height of the building from the outdoor elevation is 19.45 meters tall inclusive of the outdoor-indoor height elevation and the parapet wall, the total length is 72.0m while the total width is 16.2m.

1.2 Design Basis

1.2.1 Natural conditions

- Construction site: Hongqiao district, Tianjin city.
- Geological conditions: embedded depth of foundation: -1.8m.
- Building seismic fortification category: Category C (Class II building).
- Seismic precautionary intensity: 7.
- Design basic acceleration of ground motion: 0.15 g.
- The precautionary category: second group.
- Fire resistance rating: Class II.
- Reference wind pressure: $W_0=0.5 \text{ kN/m}^2$
- Reference snow pressure: $S_0=0.4 \text{ kN/m}^2$.
- Frozen soil depth: 60cm.

1.2.2 Structure type, building area and number of layers

- Structure type: Reinforced Concrete frame structure
- Building area: 6220.8m²
- Floor number and floor height: 3 span and 5 floors;
- Floor height: 1st – 5th floor: 3.6m
- The distance between the longitudinal columns: 6.6m
- The spans: 6.6 m + 2.7 m + 6.6 m
- Height difference between indoor and outdoor: 450mm

1.2.3 Live load standard value

- Inaccessible flat roof: 0.5kN/m²
- Room: 2.0 kN/m²
- Corridor, stairs, escape stair, bathroom and toilet: 2.5 kN/m²
- Lift mortar room: 7.0 kN/m²
- Library, storage room, art room, music room, sick room, computer room, video room, security room, maintenance room: 5.0kN/m²
- Kitchenette: 4.0kN/m²
- Staff room, meeting room, anteroom: 3.0kN/m²

1.3 Architectural drawings

Diagram 1.3-1 First floor plan

CHAPTER 1 DESIGN RESOURCES

Diagram 1.3-2 Second to fifth floor plan

Diagram 1.3-3 Front elevation plan

Diagram 1.3-4 Rear elevation plan

Diagram 1.3-5 East elevation plan

Diagram 1.3-6 Section 1-1 plan

1.4 Construction practice

The architectural construction practice is selected from the architectural < Standard Design Atlas of north China No.05J1 >.

1.4.1 Floors construction practice

Referring to Standard Design Atlas of north China No.05J1 as shown in table 1.4-1.

Table 1.4-1 Floor construction practice

Name	Material practice	Thickness (mm)	Application area
Paving floor tile (Thickness 30mm)	Paving with 8-10mm thick tiles, slurry or colored grouts	10	General floor
	20mm thick 1:4 dry cement mortar bonding layer	20	
Granite marble floor (Thickness 50mm)	20mm thick granite slab paving, slurry or colored cement grouts	20	Corridor/Entrance Hall/Non- staircase section
	30mm thick 1:4 dry cement mortar bonding layer	30	
Waterproof floor tiles (Thickness 100mm)	Paving with 8-10mm thick tiles, slurry or colored cement grouts	10	Toilet/Washroom
	25mm thick 1:4 dry cement mortar bonding layer	25	
	15mm thick cement mortar screed	15	
	50mm thick C15 fine concrete for slope where the thinnest part is not less than 30mm	50	

1.4.2 Roof construction practice

Referring to Standard Design Atlas of north China No.05J1 as shown in table 1.4-2.

Table 1.4-2 Non-accessible flat roof construction practice

Name	Material practice	Thickness (mm)	Application
	Polymer modified bitumen waterproofing membrane	3	Non-accessible flat roof
	1:3 leveling cement mortar layer	20	
	Polyphenyl insulation layer	100	
	1:8 cement expansion perlite to get 2% slope where the thinnest part is not less than 20mm	100	
	1:3 cement mortar leveling layer	20	

1.4.3 Walls construction practice

Referring to Standard Design Atlas of north China No.05J1 as shown in table 1.4-3.

Table 1.4-3 Wall construction practice

Name	Material practice	Thickness (mm)	Application area
Brick wall (thickness 30mm)	Brushing construction glue slurry once, the mixture ratio is construction glue: cement slurry = 1:4	10	All exterior walls
	15mm thick 2:1:8 cement lime mortar, twice plastered	15	
	4-5mm thick 1:1 cement mortar with water weight	5	
	15mm thick 2:1:8 cement lime mortar, twice plastered	15	
	5mm thick 1:0.5:3 cement lime mortar ratio	5	
Glazed brick wall (thickness 25mm)	Brushing construction glue slurry once, the mixture ratio is construction glue: cement slurry 1:4	10	Toilet/washroom interior wall
	15mm thick 2:1:8 cement lime mortar, twice plastered	15	

1.5 Architectural plan elevation

At the beginning of the design of the project, adhering to the principles of green architecture and humanistic architecture, the basic functions of the building are embodied in a simple way, and the functionality of the building is maximized as much as possible.

As a middle school teaching building, the entire building meets the needs of the different teaching programs by having rooms dedicated to facilitate lectures, meetings, etc. by featuring class rooms, sick bay, library, meeting room, and recreational program rooms like art, music, computer and video rooms.

In decorating, the simplest material is chosen to return the building to the original essence of the building. It has strong economic feasibility, reasonable layout and economical requirements, and meets the requirements of using functions.

The façade is beautiful in design and pleasant in appearance. The graphic design is relatively flexible and has a good orientation. The design can not only meet the functional area of the room, ventilation, lighting, etc., but also meet the psychological space and the use of space.

1.5.1 Door schedule

Door schedule as shown in table 1.5-1.

Table 1.5-1 Door schedule

Type	Design number	Size	Material	Opening method	First floor	Standard floor	Total
Door	M1821	1800X2100	Wood	Double open	13	-	13
Door	M1021	1000X2100	Wood	Single open	8	112	120

1.5.2 Window schedule

Window schedule as shown in table 1.5-2.

Table 1.5-2 Window schedule

Type	Design number	Size	Material	Opening method	First floor	Standard floor	Total
Window	C2418	2400X1800	Aluminum alloy	Sliding	24	96	120
Window	C2406	2400X600	Aluminum alloy	Sliding	2	8	10
Window	C1818	1800X1800	Aluminum alloy	Sliding	2	8	10
Window	C1218	1200X1800	Aluminum alloy	Sliding	4	16	20

CHAPTER 2 STRUCTURAL DESIGN

2.1 Structural scheme selection

2.1.1 Structure type

The structure is a reinforced concrete frame. The design life is 50 years.

2.1.2 Material selection

Main materials used:

- Concrete: Cast-in-place, C30 for all structure beams and plates and columns.
- Steel: HRB360 for all

Wall composition:

- ± 0.000 The masonry work for in filled walls above the ground are concrete hollow blocks for external walls and Autoclaved aerated concrete blocks for internal walls. The strength grade of the blocks is MU5 and the strength grade of masonry cement mortar is M7.5.

- The infill walls below the indoor surface are ordinary clay brickwork. The strength grade of the clay brick is MU10 and the strength grade of masonry cement mortar is M10.

- Ordinary clay bricks with strength grade MU10 and mixed mortar with strength grade M10 are used to build the parapet wall.

- External wall thickness: 300mm with unit weight 11.8 kN/m² and internal wall thickness: 200mm having unit weight 5.5kN/m².

- The ceiling is made of light steel keel plasterboard.

- Windows are made of plastic steel unit weight 0.3 kN/m².

- Doors are made of wood unit weight 0.2kN/m².

2.1.3 Frame column section size

The allowable axial compression ratio of the column section size to the root column is determined by the following formula.

$$\mu_c = \frac{N_c}{A_c f_c} \leq [\mu_c]$$

According to table 6.3.6 (Limit for Axial compression ratio of column) of the “Code for Seismic Design of Buildings” GB50011- 2010, the axial compression ratio limit of the frame when the earthquake resistance rating is 2 is $[\mu_c] = 0.75$. In order to make the dynamic characteristics of the structure in the two main axes similar, the column section adopts a square column, and the column axial force design value N_c is estimated as follows:

$$N_c = \gamma_G \times \beta_1 \times \beta_2 \times S \times w \times n$$

In the formula;

- w is the average gravity load value in the building area which generally takes the average value of the constant load 10~15kN/m². Standard value of main Live load, take $w=14\text{kN/m}^2$.
- S is the load area of the column sustained.
- γ_G is the partial coefficient of Dead load.
- β_1 is the additional factor generated by the horizontal force .
- β_2 is the axial force coefficient basically depending on the seismic grade of the building.
- n is the total number of storeys.

$$\begin{aligned} N_c &= \gamma_G \times \beta_1 \times \beta_2 \times S \times w \times n \\ &= 1.25 \times 1 \times 1 \times (4.65 \times 4.5) \times 14 \times 5 \\ &= 1830.94\text{kN} \end{aligned}$$

Frame columns adopts C30 concrete, so $f_c = 14.3\text{N/mm}^2$. Limit for axial compression ratio of column μ_c for seismic grade 2 is 0.75.

$$\begin{aligned} A_c &\geq \frac{N_c}{f_c \times \mu_c} \\ &\geq \frac{1830.94 \times 10^3}{14.3 \times 0.75} \\ &\geq 170717.02\text{mm}^2 \end{aligned}$$

Normally, height of frame column section $h = (1/12 \sim 1/8) H$ (H , height of frame column) and not less than 400mm, and ratio of its net length to its longer size of its section should more than 4. Width of frame column section $b = (1/1.5 \sim 1) h$ (where h is the height of

frame column section as mentioned above) and not less than 400mm. Therefore, the main building frame column section size is determined here as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 b_c h_c &\geq \sqrt{\frac{N_c}{f_c \times \mu_c}} \\
 &\geq \sqrt{170717 \text{mm}^2} \\
 &\geq 413.18 \text{mm}
 \end{aligned}$$

Using a square section, then $b_c = h_c \geq 600 \text{mm}$. Therefore, the main building frame column section size is determined as 600mm X 600mm.

2.2 Slab and beam section size

According to Section 6.3.1 of the 《Code for Seismic Design of Buildings》, the sectional dimensions of beam should meet the following requirements:

- a. The width of the beam section should not be less than 200mm.
- b. The height-width ratio of the section should not be larger than 4.
- c. The ratio between the clear span and the height of section should not be less than 4.

2.2.1 Main beams

Height of the main beams:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h &= \left(\frac{1}{8} \sim \frac{1}{14}\right) l_0 \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{8} \sim \frac{1}{14}\right) \times 4500 \\
 &= 562.5 \sim 321.4 \text{mm}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $h=600 \text{ mm}$;

Width of the main beams:

$$\begin{aligned}
 b &= \left(\frac{1}{2} \sim \frac{1}{3}\right) h \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{2} \sim \frac{1}{3}\right) \times 600 \\
 &= 300 \sim 200 \text{mm}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $b=400 \text{ mm}$.

2.2.2 Secondary beams

Height of the secondary beams:

$$h = \left(\frac{1}{12} \sim \frac{1}{18} \right) l_0$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{12} \sim \frac{1}{18} \right) \times 4500$$

$$= 375 \sim 250 \text{ mm}$$

Therefore $h = 500 \text{ mm}$;

Width of the secondary beams:

$$b = \left(\frac{1}{2} \sim \frac{1}{3} \right) h$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{2} \sim \frac{1}{3} \right) \times 500$$

$$= 250 \sim 167 \text{ mm}$$

Therefore $b = 300 \text{ mm}$.

2.2.3 Slabs

For one-way slab: ratio of span to thickness of slab shall not more than 30. The minimum thickness for a way one cast-in-situ reinforced concrete slab of a civil architecture floor is 60mm.

The depth of the slab: $h = \frac{1}{40} l_0$

$$= \frac{2250}{40}$$

$$= 56.3 \text{ mm}$$

Therefore $h = 100 \text{ mm}$.

Diagram 2.2.3-1 Layout of structural members

CHAPTER 3 LOAD CALCULATIONS

3.1 Roof dead load calculation

The roof dead load is calculated according to the construction method and is listed in Table 3-1. When analyzing the internal force of the frame structure under vertical load, the roof live load should take the larger value between the uniform live load and the snow load. For Inaccessible roof, the value is 0.50 KN/m^2 . In the seismic calculation, when calculating the representative value of roof gravity load, the roof live load is not considered, and snow load. The value of the snow live load is 0.40 KN/m^2 as shown in table 3.1-1.

Table 3.1-1 Roof Dead Load Calculation

Name and application area	Material practice	Thickness (mm)	Unit weight (kN/m^2)	Weight (kN/m^2)	Standard value of dead load (kN/m^2)
Non-accessible flat roof	Ceiling			0.2	5.4
	Polymer modified bitumen waterproofing membrane	3		0.1	
	1:3 leveling cement mortar layer	20	20	0.4	
	Polyphenyl insulation layer	100	3	0.3	
	1:8 cement expansion perlite to get 2% slope where the thinnest part is not less than 20mm	100	15	1.5	
	1:3 cement mortar leveling layer	20		0.4	
	Reinforced concrete floor	100	25	2.5	

3.2 Floor dead load calculations

The floor dead load is calculated according to the construction method and is listed in Table 3.2-1

Table 3.2-1 Floor Dead Load Calculation

Name and application area	Material practice	Thickness (mm)	Unit weight (kN/m ²)	Weight (kN/m ²)	Standard value of dead load (kN/m ²)	Floor area on first floor (m ²)	Floor area on standard floor (m ²)
Paving Tile floor (Thickness 30mm) General floor	Paving with 10mm thick tiles, slurry or colored grouts	10	20	0.2	3.25	745.2	776.25
	20mm thick 1:4 dry cement mortar bonding layer	20	20	0.4			
	Light steel PVC Ceiling	8	18.75	0.15			
	Reinforced concrete floor	100	25	2.5			
Granite Marble floor (Thickness 50mm) Corridor/ Entrance hall/non-staircase section	20mm thick granite slab paving, Slurry or colored cements grouts	20	28	0.56	4.06	265.95	203.85
	30mm thick 1:4 dry cement mortar bonding layer	30	20	0.6			
	Ceiling Bottom board of Light Steel Keel	20	20	0.4			
	Reinforced concrete floor	100	25	2.5			
Waterproof Tiles Floor (Thickness 102mm) Toilet/ Washroom	Paving with 10mm thick tiles, slurry or colored cement grouts	10	20	0.1	5	124.2	124.2
	25mm thick 1:4 dry cement mortar bonding layer	25	20	0.5			
	Ceiling			0.5			
	15mm thick cement mortar screed	15	20	0.3			
	50mm thick C15 fine concrete for slope where the thinnest part is not less than 30mm	50	20	1			
	Reinforced concrete floor	100	25	2.5			

3.3 Partition walls dead load calculations

Height of the floor \times Thickness of the wall \times Density of material
 $h \times t \times d$

All floors

The dead load from the outer partition wall is:

$$3.6\text{m} \times 0.30\text{m} \times 10\text{kN/m}^2 \\ = 10.8 \text{ kN/m}$$

The dead load of the inner partition wall is:

$$3.6\text{m} \times 0.20\text{m} \times 10 \text{ kN/m}^2 \\ = 7.2 \text{ kN/m}$$

3.4 Parapet wall dead load calculations

Height of the parapet wall \times Thickness of the parapet wall \times Density of material
 $h \times t \times d$

The dead load of the parapet is:

$$1.0\text{m} \times 0.30\text{m} \times 10 \text{ kN/m}^2 \\ = 3.0 \text{ kN/m}$$

3.5 Live load standard value

- Inaccessible flat roof: 0.5kN/m^2
- Room: 2.0kN/m^2
- Corridor, stairs, escape stair, bathroom and toilet: 2.5kN/m^2
- Staff room, meeting room, anteroom, library, storage room, art room, music room, sick room, computer room, video room, security room, maintenance room, Kitchenette: 3.5kN/m^2
- Lift mortar room: 7.0kN/m^2

3.6 Load check of the first floor

The dead loads are 3.25kN/m^2 , 4.06kN/m^2 and 5kN/m^2 , live loads are 0.5kN/m^2 , 2.0kN/m^2 , 2.5kN/m^2 , 3.5kN/m^2 and 7.0kN/m^2 and self-weight of the slab is 2.5 kN/m^2 .

The distribution loads on the outer main beams are 10.8kN/m and inner beams are 7.2kN/m while the distribution loads on the parapet wall are 3.0kN/m as shown in diagram 3.6-1.

Diagram 3.6-1 Loads of the first floor

CHAPTER 4 YJK STRUCTURAL DESIGN

4.1 Total information of the structure

Type of structure:	Frame
Structure Material Information:	Reinforced Concrete
Structure region:	Nationwide
Number of the basement layer:	0
The floor of structural fixed ends (on the top):	0
The maximum bottom elevation of member joined with foundations (m):	0.000
Podium floors:	0
The floor number of transition-stories:	0
The floor number of strengthened stories:	0
Vertical load calculating information:	Multi Load Type 1
Wind Load calculating Information:	Default
Seismic force calculating information:	Hor. and Ver. by Code Simplified Method
Calculating crane load or not:	no
Calculating civil air defence load or not:	no
Calculating prestressing equivalent load or not:	no
Generating data for contouring or not:	no
Calculating temperature load or not:	no
Wall Axis-stiff calculation of vertical load considering the shrinkage and creep:	no
Generating stiffness to foundations or not:	no
Up-ground analysis consider foundation stiffness:	no
The Construction Simulation loaded layer step:	1
Consider stiff of infilled-wall:	no
Adopt general Code	yes

4.2 Calculating control information

Angle of horizontal force (Rad) with universal coordinate system (°)	0.00
The stiffness amplification coefficient of the beams, confirm the value based on Concrete Code of 2010	no
Stiffness amplification coefficient of mid-beams	1.00
Upper limit of side-beams stiffness amplification coefficient	1.50
Coupling beams stiffness reduction coefficient (earthquake)	0.70
Coupling beams stiffness reduction coefficient(wind)	1.00
Coupling beams according to wall element calculation control span height ration	4.00
Ordinary Coupling beam's Concrete grade same to wall	yes
Max controlling size of bin-divisible of wall element(m)	1.00
Max controlling size of bin-divisible of slab element(m)	1.00
Short wall limb automatically encryption	yes
Load transmit way of elastic slab	Planar Transmition
Membrane element type	Classical Membrane Element(QA4)
The overlapping portions of the beams are simplified to rigid zone or not	no
The overlapping portions of the columns are simplified to rigid zone or not	no
Wall beams midspan nodal points as rigid floor follow nodal points	yes
Calculating structure considering stair stiffness	no
The compatibility of deformation beams and	

elastic slab	yes
Beam eccentricity to slab	no
Rigid floor suppose	Not Execute Rigid Floor Suppose
Basement ceiling must execute rigid floor assumption	no
Automatic partition multi-tower or not	no
Element seismic force calculated by elastic slab 6 moduling	no
Calculating sita-slab weight automatically	yes
Calculating cast-in-situ hollow slab	no
Increase calculation coupling beams stiffness not reduction model of earthquake displacement	no
Deduct column overlap with beam and wall	no
Deduct slab overlap with beam and wall	no
Displacement output of the nodal points or not	no
Considering the effect of P-Delt or not	no
Overall Imperfections	no
Set effective length factor to 1	no
Consider beam element P-Delta effect;	no
Buckling analysis sign	no
Start parallel solver	yes
CPU num(0-auto)	-2
Memory size(MB,0-auto)	0
Parameter of user defined	
Solver kind	Pardiso Couple
Load step num	1
Iterating num	30
Displacement control	yes
Precision of displacement	0.0010
Load control	yes
Precision of Load	0.0010

4.3 Wind load information

Use the specified directly wind tunnel test results:	no
Multi-dir wind angles	
Execute code:	GB50009-2012
Ground roughness:	A
Revised basic wind (kN/m ²):	0.50
Calculating wind load with damping ratio %):	5.0
Structure X natural period (S):	0.20
Structure Y natural period (S):	0.20
Load-bearing capacity design wind load effect amplification coefficient:	1.0
Wind pressure for Checking human comfortbaleness(kN/m ²)	0.50
Structure damping ratio for Checking human comfortbaleness(%)	2.0
Considering along-wind dynamic:	yes
Multi-dir wind angles:	
Considering transverse wind vibration	no
Consider torsion wind induced oscillation	no
Automatic calculation the width and depth of structure	yes
Wind load shape coefficient subsection counts	1
First subsection	
Max-Flr:	5
X-Front:	0.80
X-Back:	-0.50
X-Side:	0.00
X-Shield:	1.00
Y-Front:	0.80
Y-Back:	-0.50
Y-Side:	0.00
Y-Shield:	1.00

4.4 Earthquake information

Design earthquake group:	Second
Design by GB18306-2015:	yes
Seismic Intensity:	7 (0.15g)
Site Classification:	II
Characteristic Period:	0.40
Reduction coefficient of Period	1.00
The type of eigenvalues analysis:	WYD-RITZ
Determining the method of the number of modes:	User Definition
User define mode number:	15
Internal force sign determined by main Eigen mode:	no
Frame seismic classification	Second Grade
Seismic classification of shear wall	Third Grade
Steel framed seismic classification	Third Grade
Details for seismic design of seismic classification	Not Change
The seismic grade of shear wall structure supported on frame bottom strengthened area shear wall automatically increase one level	Yes
Seismic grade of seismic details design decrease by step and	
Seismic grade of seismic measures 4	Yes
Determining the method of damping ratio:	All Floors Unify
Structure damping ratio (%):	5.0
Consider accidental eccentric or not:	no
Considering bidirectional seismic torsional effect or not:	no
Automatic computing the most unfavorable earthquake direction effect:	no
The additional number of earthquake oblique crossing lateral force resisting member direction:	0
Live load gravity load central value combination coefficient:	0.50
The maximum strong motion coefficient of earthquake:	0.125
The maximum strong motion coefficient of the rare earthquake:	0.712
Earthquake analysis without mass-basement:	no

Curve of earthquake influence coefficient custom:	no
Earthquake function amplification method:	All Floors Unify
All stories seismic force amplification coefficient:	1.00
Performance-Based Design:	no

4.5 Design information

According to the seismic code 5.2.5 adjust floor seismic force or not:	yes
Torsion effect is obvious or not:	no
Automatically calculating dynamic displacement ratio:	no
The first translation period direction dynamic displacement ratio (zero~one):	0.50
The second translation period direction dynamic displacement ratio(zero~one):	0.50
0.2V0 adjusting without beam	no
Whether the user specifies the 0.2V0 adjustment Coefficient Regular of 0.2V0 adjustment	no Min(0.20*Vo, 1.50*Vfmax)
Minimum Coefficient of floor V for 0.2V0	0.20
Maximum Coefficient of Frame V for 0.2V0	1.50
Adjust subsection counts of 0.2V0	0
Adjust upper limit of 0.2V0	2.00
Force adjust method of bidirectional earthquake	First consideration of bi-directional seismic readjustment
State shear force of wall-end column to wall	0
Extra reinforcement coe	1.15
Adjust upper limit of Frame-supporting Column	5.00
Judge Weak-Layer with the method of Storey Stiffness Ratio	Conform to JGJ3-2010 and GB50011-2010 Strictly

At the bottom of the build fixed floors stiffness ratio execute	
High Code 3.5.2-2:	no
Automaticity for layer shear capacity mutagenesis weak layer amplification adjustment:	no
Automaticity adjust reinforcement by shear capacity ratio:	no
Transition- stories is Weak-Layer or not:	yes
Seismic Internal Forces of Weak-Layer Amplification coefficient:	1.25
Modification coefficient of Negative moment of the beam	0.85
Min-moment coefficient of frame beam to hinged beam	0.50
Min-moment coefficient of non-frame beam to hinged beam	0.33
Reduction coefficient for beams torsion	0.40
Extra reinforcement coe	1.15
Max Z-angle of brace (angle) (Brace which angle between the vertical axis is less than the value is designed as column)	20
Stat earthquake floor shear by vertical member force	no
Dis-ratio 1 when Dis-angle less then this value	0.00020
Shear-walls are assumed to bear all seismic shear force:	no

4.6 Live load information

Reduction for live load on col. & wall:	no
Live-load Reduction of Floor Beams:	No Reduction
Considering the most top floor of Live-load Unfavorable Distribution:	0
Beam Live-load internal force amplification coefficient:	1.00

4.7 Member design information

Column reinforcement calculation principle:	Single-Biased
Max dia by Double-Biased	32
Coupling beams with the design of symmetrical reinforcement:	no
Frame beam end reinforcement considering Compression reinforcement when seismic design:	yes

Rectangular concrete beams in accordance with T-typed beams reinforcement:	no
According to simplified calculation Shear-Span Ratio ($H_n/2h_0$):	yes
Column-shear-wall reinforcement design considering boundary columns:	no
Column-shear-wall reinforcement design considering wing walls:	no
Shear wall outside connected beams according to the frame beams design:	yes
The Checking of one level seismic wall construction joints:	yes
Concrete beam bending design control ratio of axial force to section and axial strength under earthquake forces:	0.40
Beam-end reinforcement internal force position (zero-nodal points, one- Support edge):	0.00
Steel member section net gross area ratio	0.85
X-Dir steel column length is calculated according to displacement calculation or not:	yes
Y-Dir steel column length is calculated according to displacement calculation or not:	yes
According to Steel Code 5.3.3-2 automatically judge strong or weak support:	no
According to «Technical code for steel structure of light-weight building with gabled frames» appendix A.0.8:	no
Non seismic frame column axial compression ratio calculated by gravity load:	no
The frame column axial compression ratio limit according to the frame structure:	no
Nominal cover of beams(mm):	20
Nominal cover of column(mm):	20
Reinforcing Area in the bottom is restricted edge member:	no
The max length of shadow region of Shear Wall Restricted edge member to $\lambda / 2$:	0.00
Out-plan beam bottom generating hidden column edge member:	Generate all
The distance of the combine of edge members:	300

The distance of the combine of short-pier edge members:	600
The size of edge member is whole modulus:	10
The design consideration of structure edge member size:	The 7.2.16 item of Technical Specification for Concrete Structures of Tall Building JGJ 3-2010
Edge member design by DBJ15-92-2013:	no
Load of composite beam (kN/m ²)	1.50
The design consideration of Steel-reinforced concrete member:	JGJ138-2016
Design by «Technical specification for steel structure of tall building» JGJ99-2015:	yes
Tube-reinforced concrete column force ratio:	0.00
Use GB50017-2017:	yes
Control section width ratio according to steel structure specification:	yes
Control section width ratio according to steel structure specification:	yes
Section width grade:	S3
Section width grade of brace:	S3

4.8 Envelope design

Whether points tower and the overall are calculated respectively, taking greater:	no
Get the larger result of the model of frame and frame-wall:	no
Envelope design with other project:	no

4.9 Appraisal and strengthening

Appraisal and Strengthening:	no
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4.10 Precast concrete structure

Precast concrete structure: no

4.11 Material information

Unit weight of concrete(kN/m ³):	25.00
Unit weight of masonry(kN/m ³):	22.00
Unit weight of steel(kN/m ³):	78.00
Unit weight of light weight aggregate concrete(kN/m ³):	18.50
Density of light weight aggregate concrete:	1800
Beams stirrup spacing(mm):	100
Column stirrup spacing(mm):	100
Maximum space of wall horizontal distribution steel (mm):	200
Minimum space of wall vertical distribution steel (%):	0.30
Minimum space of wall horizontal distribution steel (%):	0.20
The bottom of structure separately specified wall vertical distribution reinforcement rate of the layer:	no
Wall vertical distribution steel reinforcement ratio of structure bottom	
Separately specified floor:	0.60

4.12 Steel strength

The steel strength design values of HPB300(N/mm ²):	270
The steel strength design values of HRB335(N/mm ²):	300
The steel strength design values of HRB400(N/mm ²):	360

4.13 Basement information

Proportional coefficient of horizontal resistance coefficient:	10.00
Deducting the ground several layer backfill constraint:	0
Cover of basement wall(mm):	35
Unit weight of backfill:	18.00

Lateral earth pressure coefficient of backfill:	0.50
Outdoor horizon elevation:	-0.35
Underground water level elevation:	-20.00
Outside ground additional load (kN/m ²):	0.00
Load combination style of basement water:	Superposition
Lateral earth pressure style:	Roof bidirectional spring
Earthquake reaction analyzing by Reaction displacement method:	no

4.14 Load combination

The importance coefficient of structure:	1.00
User defined Load combination:	no
User defined Load combination of PM module:	no
Safety factor for dead load:	1.30
Safety factor for Live load:	1.50
Live load combination coefficient:	0.70
Live load frequent coefficient:	0.60
Live load quasi coefficient:	0.50
Considering structural design service life of live load adjustment coefficient:	1.00
Safety factor for wind load:	1.50
Wind load combination coefficient:	0.60
Wind load frequent coefficient:	0.40
Wind load participate in seism combination or not:	no
Safety factor for gravity:	1.30
Safety factor for horizontal earthquake force:	1.40
Safety factor for vertical earthquake:	0.50
Considering the main combination of vertical earthquake or not:	yes

CHAPTER 5 BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE STRUCTURE

5.1 Floors attribute

Floor attribute shown in table 5.1-1.

Table 5.1-1 Floors attribute

Floor	Tower	Attribute
5	1	Standard floor 3
4	1	Standard floor 2
3	1	Standard floor 2
2	1	Standard floor 2
1	1	Standard floor 1

5.2 Towers attribute

Tower attribute shown in table 5.2-1.

Table 5.2-1 Towers attribute

Tower	Attribute	Value
1	Type of structure	Frame
	Structure X natural period(s)	0.20
	Structure Y natural period(s)	0.20
	Optimization subsection of horizontal wind load	1
	Subsection	1
	Max-Flr	5
	Shield	1.00
	Front	0.80
	Back	-0.50
	Side	0.00
	Adjust subsection counts of 0.2V0	0
	Minimum Coefficient of floor V for 0.2V0	0.20
	Maximum Coefficient of frame V for 0.2V0	1.50

5.3 Member statistics

Member statistics shown from table 5.3-1 to table 5.3-4.

**Table 5.3-1 The Number of Every Floor Members, Member Materials and Floor Height
(units:m)**

Floor	Tower	Beams	Columns	Braces	Wall	Floor height (m)	Add up height (m)
5	1	181	68	0	0	3.600	18.000
4	1	174	68	0	0	3.600	14.400
3	1	174	68	0	0	3.600	10.800
2	1	174	68	0	0	3.600	7.200
1	1	174	68	0	0	3.600	3.600

Table 5.3-2 Cover (units:mm)

Floor	Tower	Beams (mm)	Columns (mm)	Walls (mm)
5	1	20	20	0
4	1	20	20	0
3	1	20	20	0
2	1	20	20	0
1	1	20	20	0

Table 5.3-3 Concrete member

Floor	Tower	Beams (Con./Main Bar)	Columns (Con./Main Bar)	Braces (Con./Main Bar)	Walls (Con./Main Bar)
5	1	115(C30/360)	68(C30/360)	0(C0/0)	0(C0/0)
4	1	115(C30/360)	68(C30/360)	0(C0/0)	0(C0/0)
3	1	115(C30/360)	68(C30/360)	0(C0/0)	0(C0/0)
2	1	115(C30/360)	68(C30/360)	0(C0/0)	0(C0/0)
1	1	115(C30/360)	68(C30/360)	0(C0/0)	0(C0/0)

Table 5.3-4 Stirrup (Wall distribution steel)

Floor	Tower	Beams (Stirrup)	Columns (Stirrup)	Braces (Stirrup)	Walls (Horizontal/Vertical)	Edge members (Stirrup)
5	1	115(C30/360)	68(360)	0(0)	0(0/0)	(270)
4	1	115(C30/360)	68(360)	0(0)	0(0/0)	(270)
3	1	115(C30/360)	68(360)	0(0)	0(0/0)	(270)
2	1	115(C30/360)	68(360)	0(0)	0(0/0)	(270)
1	1	115(C30/360)	68(360)	0(0)	0(0/0)	(270)

5.4 Floor mass

Floor mass shown in table 5.4-1 and table 5.4-2.

Table 5.4-1 Every Floor Center-of-Mass Coordinate

Floor	Tower	Mass X	Mass Y	Mass Z
5	1	36.150	8.258	18.000
4	1	36.150	8.498	14.400
3	1	36.150	8.498	10.800
2	1	36.150	8.498	7.200
1	1	36.249	8.473	3.600

According to 《Technical specification for concrete structures of tall building》 (JGJ 3-2010) 3.5.6, the mass of floor should be evenly distributed along the height and it should not be greater than 1.5 times that of the adjacent lower floor.

All structure floor meet the specification requirements.

Table 5.4-2 Every floor quality and floor mass ratio

Floor	Tower	Dead load mass (t)	Live load mass (t)	Live load mass (No Reduction)(t)	Additional load mass (t)	Mass Ratio	Ratio judgment
5	1	1179.2	116.6	233.3	0.0	0.5	Satisfying
4	1	1316.0	130.3	260.5	0.0	1.00	Satisfying
3	1	1316.0	130.3	260.5	0.0	1.00	Satisfying
2	1	1316.0	130.3	260.5	0.0	0.96	Satisfying
1	1	1319.5	130.3	260.5	0.0	1.00	Satisfying
Total	-	6446.8	637.7	1275.5	0.0		

Dead load total mass(t): 6446.754.754

Live load total mass (t): 637.739

Addition total mass(t): 0.000

Structure total mass(t): 7084.493

Dead load total mass including structure dead load and additional dead load

Live load mass = live load gravity load representative value coefficient * live load equivalent mass

Total mass=dead load mass +live load mass + additional load mass

Diagram 5.4-1 The distribution curve of Dead load, Live load, Floor mass(Tower 1)

Diagram 5.4-2 The distribution curve of Mass Ratio(Tower 1)

5.5 Floor size, Unit mass

Floor size, unit mass shown in tables 5.5-1 and table 5.5-2.

Table 5.5-1 Equivalent size of each floor (units m,m²)

Floor	Tower	Area	Center X	Center Y	Equi. B	Equi. H	Max BMAX	Min BMIN
5	1	1166.40	36.15	8.26	72.00	16.20	72.00	16.20
4	1	1042.20	36.15	8.26	72.00	16.20	72.00	16.20
3	1	1042.20	36.15	8.26	72.00	16.20	72.00	16.20
2	1	1042.20	36.15	8.26	72.00	16.20	72.00	16.20
1	1	1042.20	36.15	8.26	72.00	16.20	72.00	16.20

Mass of unit area: $g[i]$

Mass of unit area ratio: $\max(g[i]/g[i-1],g[i]/g[i+1])$

Table 5.5-2 Weight of each floor and unit area distribution (units kg/m²)

Floor	Tower	Floor mass	Mass of unit area g	Mass of unit area ratio max
5	1	1.30E+006	1110.95	0.80
4	1	1.45E+006	1387.73	1.25
3	1	1.45E+006	1387.73	1.00
2	1	1.45E+006	1387.73	1.00
1	1	1.45E+006	1391.11	1.00

5.6 Software version

Software version: 4.3.0

CHAPTER 6 PERIODS AND MODE

6.1 Basic results of vibration mode

Basic results of vibration mode shown in table 6.1-1 and 6.1-2

Table 6.1-1 Periods considering lateral-torsion coupling(s), Translational coefficient X,Y Torsion coefficient

Mode	Period	Angle	Movement (X+Y)	Movement(z)
1	0.8221	90.00	1.00(0.00+1.00)	0.00
2	0.7681	0.94	0.00(0.00+0.00)	1.00
3	0.5664	-0.00	1.00(1.00+0.00)	0.00
4	0.2443	90.00	1.00(0.00+1.00)	0.00
5	0.2312	10.54	0.00(0.00+0.00)	1.00
6	0.1813	-0.00	1.00(1.00+0.00)	0.00
7	0.1238	90.02	1.00(0.00+1.00)	0.00
8	0.1191	25.31	0.00(0.00+0.00)	1.00
9	0.1026	180.00	1.00(1.00+0.00)	0.00
10	0.0773	90.10	1.00(0.00+1.00)	0.00
11	0.0753	22.12	0.01(0.01+0.00)	0.99
12	0.0706	179.96	0.99(0.99+0.00)	0.01
13	0.0577	90.33	1.00(0.00+1.00)	0.00
14	0.0567	1.99	0.42(0.42+0.00)	0.58
15	0.0561	179.15	0.59(0.58+0.00)	0.41

Table 6.1-2 Mass coefficient

Mode	Movement mass X %(sum)	Movement mass Y %(sum)	Movement mass Z %(sum)
1	0.00%(0.00%)	79.61%(79.61%)	0.00%(0.00%)
2	0.02%(0.02%)	0.00%(79.61%)	76.85%(76.85%)
3	83.42%(83.44%)	0.00%(79.61%)	0.02%(76.86%)
4	0.00%(83.44%)	12.18%(91.79%)	0.00%(76.87%)
5	0.00%(83.44%)	0.00%(91.79%)	9.87%(86.73%)
6	10.30%(93.75%)	0.00%(91.79%)	0.01%(86.74%)
7	0.00%(93.75%)	4.95%(96.74%)	0.00%(86.74%)
8	0.00%(93.75%)	0.00%(96.74%)	5.06%(91.80%)
9	3.96%(97.71%)	0.00%(96.74%)	0.00%(91.80%)
10	0.00%(97.71%)	2.45%(99.19%)	0.00%(91.80%)
11	0.01%(97.72%)	0.00%(99.20%)	1.97%(93.77%)
12	1.77%(99.49%)	0.00%(99.20%)	0.01%(93.79%)
13	0.00%(99.49%)	0.80%(100.00%)	0.00%(93.79%)
14	0.21%(99.70%)	0.00%(100.00%)	0.47%(94.26%)
15	0.30%(100.00%)	0.00%(100.00%)	0.32%(94.57%)

Torsion(Z) coefficient will work only in forced rigid floor, while to no-rigid floor the calculation result is only for reference

According to 《High code》 5.1.21, the sum of the mass of each modal participation should not be less than 90% of the total mass.

The sum of translation modal participation mass coefficient in the direction of X: 100.00%

The sum of translation modal participation mass coefficient in the direction of Y: 100.00%

The first torsion period(0.7681)/The first translation period(0.8221) = 0.93

The direction of maximum earthquake action = 90.001°

6.2 Model damping ratio

Model damping ratio shown in table 6.2-1.

Table 6.2-1 Model damping ratio

Model	Damping ratio
1-15	0.05

6.3 Floor reaction force of Single mode under earthquake action X,Y

6.3.1 The calculation results of no-rigid floor assumption mode

F-x-x : The component of coupling seismic force X in the X direction

F-x-y : The component of coupling seismic force X in the Y direction

F-x-t : The torsion of coupling seismic force X

This is shown from tables 6.3.1-1 to table 6.3.1-15

Table 6.3.1-1 Model 1 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.00	-0.36	-0.15
4	1	0.00	-0.33	-0.14
3	1	0.00	-0.25	-0.11
2	1	0.00	-0.15	-0.07
1	1	0.00	-0.06	-0.02

Table 6.3.1-2 Model 2 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.39	0.59	-572.64
4	1	0.47	0.44	-504.81
3	1	0.37	0.33	-386.53
2	1	0.23	0.20	-237.83
1	1	0.09	0.14	-89.79

Table 6.3.1-3 Model 3 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	1552.02	-0.23	619.65
4	1	1447.94	-0.11	539.27
3	1	1134.39	-0.08	408.44
2	1	717.82	-0.05	249.61
1	1	282.25	-0.09	93.98

Table 6.3.1-4 Model 4 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	-0.00	0.16	0.04
4	1	-0.00	0.01	0.01
3	1	0.00	-0.14	-0.03
2	1	0.00	-0.18	-0.04
1	1	0.00	-0.09	-0.02

Table 6.3.1-5 Model 5 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	-0.62	-0.26	566.48
4	1	-0.15	0.01	52.82
3	1	0.50	0.17	-443.45
2	1	0.73	0.23	-583.22
1	1	0.41	0.39	-314.11

Table 6.3.1-6 Model 6 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	-1025.46	0.09	-536.96
4	1	-149.19	-0.01	-5.29
3	1	809.38	-0.02	476.39
2	1	1119.32	-0.05	591.47
1	1	625.36	-0.30	312.18

Table 6.3.-7 Model 7 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.00	0.32	-0.14
4	1	-0.00	-0.36	0.14
3	1	-0.00	-0.32	0.18
2	1	0.00	0.32	-0.08
1	1	0.00	0.42	-0.20

Table 6.3.1-8 Model 8 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	2.09	-0.74	-703.85
4	1	-2.05	0.93	711.48
3	1	-2.18	0.60	656.42
2	1	1.81	-1.06	-641.18
1	1	2.69	-0.26	-867.73

Table 6.3.1-9 Model 9 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	512.82	0.43	672.66
4	1	-514.62	-0.60	-743.87
3	1	-524.94	-0.29	-654.89
2	1	449.43	0.77	655.53
1	1	661.53	-0.19	873.16

Table 6.3.1-10 Model 10 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	-0.00	-0.66	0.74
4	1	0.00	1.51	-1.59
3	1	-0.00	-0.93	0.68
2	1	-0.00	-0.67	1.14
1	1	0.01	1.66	-1.44

Table 6.3.1-11 Model 11 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	-60.00	4.45	2001.09
4	1	129.73	-10.89	-4263.30
3	1	-72.56	8.57	2599.20
2	1	-63.61	1.80	1923.19
1	1	140.30	-9.84	-4706.44

Table 6.3.1-12 Model 12 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	-150.11	-3.82	-1979.62
4	1	325.01	9.44	4263.30
3	1	-182.17	-7.68	-2602.05
2	1	-159.39	-1.12	-1920.02
1	1	352.01	8.20	4698.08

Table 6.3.1-13 Model 13 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.00	-0.06	0.00
4	1	-0.00	0.18	-0.02
3	1	0.00	-0.28	0.01
2	1	-0.00	0.29	0.03
1	1	0.00	-0.24	-0.14

Table 6.3.1-14 Model 14 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	45.86	0.14	-118.50
4	1	-137.66	-0.41	336.02
3	1	202.42	0.55	-508.36
2	1	-208.72	-0.43	533.84
1	1	163.83	0.21	-434.70

Table 6.3.1-15 Model 15 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-x-x (kN)	F-x-y (kN)	F-x-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.66	-0.07	113.19
4	1	-1.99	0.19	-333.55
3	1	2.93	-0.23	504.80
2	1	-3.03	0.11	-529.54
1	1	2.38	0.05	429.02

6.3.2 The calculation results of no-rigid floor assumption mode

F-y-x : The component of coupling seismic force Y in the direction of X

F-y-y : The component of coupling seismic force Y in the direction of Y

F-y-t : The torsion of coupling seismic force Y

This is shown from tables 6.3.2-1 to table 6.3.2-15

Table 6.3.2-1 Model 1 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	-0.26	1382.39	595.93
4	1	-0.36	1253.89	528.42
3	1	-0.28	955.75	406.35
2	1	-0.18	585.19	250.12
1	1	-0.07	218.95	93.80

Table 6.3.2-2 Model 2 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.43	0.65	-633.38
4	1	0.52	0.49	-558.36
3	1	0.41	0.37	-427.53
2	1	0.26	0.22	-263.06
1	1	0.10	0.16	-99.31

Table 6.3.2-3 Model 3 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	-0.17	0.00	-0.07
4	1	-0.16	0.00	-0.06
3	1	-0.12	0.00	-0.04
2	1	-0.08	0.00	-0.03
1	1	-0.03	0.00	-0.01

Table 6.3.2-4 Model 4 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.16	-1080.92	-280.65
4	1	0.05	-81.17	-43.13
3	1	-0.14	901.54	189.70
2	1	-0.20	1166.30	243.21
1	1	-0.11	621.37	109.55

Table 6.3.2-5 Model 5 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	-0.38	-0.16	345.97
4	1	-0.09	0.00	32.26
3	1	0.31	0.10	-270.83
2	1	0.45	0.14	-356.19
1	1	0.25	0.24	-191.84

Table 6.3.2-6 Model 6 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.22	-0.00	0.12
4	1	0.03	0.00	0.00
3	1	-0.18	0.00	-0.10
2	1	-0.25	0.00	-0.13
1	1	-0.14	0.00	-0.07

Table 6.3.2-7 Model 7 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.34	517.88	-221.73
4	1	-0.32	-567.04	228.22
3	1	-0.37	-506.57	279.50
2	1	0.29	509.83	-127.58
1	1	0.45	676.83	-324.37

Table 6.3.1-8 Model 8 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	-0.46	0.16	156.04
4	1	0.45	-0.21	-157.74
3	1	0.48	-0.13	-145.53
2	1	-0.40	0.23	142.15
1	1	-0.60	0.06	192.38

Table 6.3.2-9 Model 9 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.10	0.00	0.13
4	1	-0.10	-0.00	-0.15
3	1	-0.10	-0.00	-0.13
2	1	0.09	0.00	0.13
1	1	0.13	-0.00	0.17

Table 6.3.2-10 Model 10 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	-0.71	-209.75	236.16
4	1	1.54	480.41	-505.53
3	1	-0.85	-296.87	217.69
2	1	-0.78	-213.74	364.57
1	1	1.72	529.39	-460.61

Table 6.3.2-11 Model 11 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	4.80	-0.36	-160.02
4	1	-10.37	0.87	340.92
3	1	5.80	-0.69	-207.85
2	1	5.09	-0.14	-153.79
1	1	-11.22	0.79	376.35

Table 6.3.2-12 Model 12 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	-4.05	-0.10	-53.48
4	1	8.78	0.26	115.16
3	1	-4.92	-0.21	-70.29
2	1	-4.31	-0.03	-51.87
1	1	9.51	0.22	126.91

Table 6.3.2-13 Model 13 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	-0.08	45.66	-3.86
4	1	0.24	-143.42	17.76
3	1	-0.35	218.03	-10.20
2	1	0.34	-229.40	-21.29
1	1	-0.25	185.82	109.28

Table 6.3.2-14 Model 14 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.03	0.00	-0.09
4	1	-0.10	-0.00	0.24
3	1	0.15	0.00	-0.37
2	1	-0.15	-0.00	0.39
1	1	0.12	0.00	-0.32

Table 6.3.2-15 Model 15 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	F-y-x (kN)	F-y-y (kN)	F-y-t (kN-m)
5	1	0.04	-0.00	6.36
4	1	-0.11	0.01	-18.74
3	1	0.16	-0.01	28.36
2	1	-0.17	0.01	-29.75
1	1	0.13	0.00	24.10

6.4 Floor reaction force of Single mode under earthquake action X,Y

Floor reaction force of Single mode under earthquake action X,Y is shown in table 6.4-1

Table 6.4-1 X-Shear force in X earthquake action,Y-Shear force in Y earthquake action under each vibration mode (units:kN) 15 earthquake force

Floor	Tower	Mode	X-Shear force	Y-Shear force
1	1	1	0.00	4396.17
		2	1.54	1.89
		3	5134.42	0.00
		4	0.00	1527.12
		5	0.87	0.32
		6	1379.41	0.00
		7	0.00	630.94
		8	2.36	0.12
		9	584.22	0.00
		10	0.00	289.44
		11	73.86	0.47
		12	185.34	0.14
		13	0.00	76.68
		14	65.74	0.00
		15	0.95	0.00

6.5 Results after CQC combination in X,Y earthquake action

Applied force X of every floor(CQC)

F_x(kN): Structure seismic response force under earthquake action X

V_x(kN): Structure floor shear under earthquake action X

M_x(kN-m): Structure bending moment under earthquake action X

sF_x(kN): Floor X-force of base shear method

《Seismic Code》 5.2.5, Floor Min shear-weight ratio in X direction of seismic code = 2.50%

By the following table 6.5-1 shows, Floor Shear-weight Ratio in X direction comply with the code.

Table 6.5-1 Applied force X of every floor(CQC)

Floor	Tower	F _x	V _x (Divide To. Shear/weight)	M _x	sF _x
5	1	1930.06	1930.06(10.256%)	6948.23	1727.08
4	1	1605.23	3225.88(8.350%)	18245.36	1454.88
3	1	1520.38	4184.18(7.159%)	32564.71	1091.16
2	1	1446.44	4922.18(6.289%)	49153.51	727.44
1	1	1123.35	5370.34(5.434%)	67268.29	377.31

Applied force Y of every floor(CQC)

F_y(kN): Structure seismic response force under earthquake action Y

V_y(kN): Structure floor shear under earthquake action Y

M_y(kN-m): Structure bending moment in earthquake action Y

sF_y(kN): Floor Y-force of base shear method

《Seismic Code》 5.2.5, Floor Min shear-weight ratio in Y direction of seismic code = 2.50%

By the following table 6.5-2 shows, Floor Shear-weight Ratio in Y direction comply with the code.

Table 6.5-2 Applied force Y of every floor(CQC)

Floor	Tower	F _y	V _y (Divide To. Shear/weight)	M _y	sF _y
5	1	1831.14	1831.14(9.731%)	6592.09	1513.82
4	1	1455.73	2890.30(7.481%)	16612.60	1275.23
3	1	1450.46	3645.93(6.238%)	28813.54	956.42
2	1	1443.87	4288.42(5.479%)	42821.23	637.61
1	1	1133.01	4722.46(4.779%)	58313.78	330.72

Diagram 6.5-1 Sketch of Shear-weight Ratio in seismic conditions(Tower 1)

Floor reaction force of Single mode under earthquake action Z

Z direction seismic force(code simplified method)

F-z-z : The component of seismic force in the Z direction

This is shown in table 6.5-3.

Table 6.5-3 Z direction seismic force(code simplified method)

Floor	Tower	F-z-z (kN)
5	1	- 2900.83
4	1	- 244.64
3	1	- 1832.73
2	1	- 1221.82
1	1	- -633.73

CHAPTER 7 FLOOR WIND LOAD, STATISTICAL RESULTS OF EARTHQUAKE ACTION

7.1 Wind load information

Wind unit: kN/m²

Wind load, Floor shear unit: kN

Floor Moment unit: kN.m

This is shown in table 7.1-1

Table 7.1-1 Wind load information

Floor	Tower	In X direction			In Y direction		
		Wind	Shear	Overturn Bending Moment	Wind	Shear	Overturn Bending Moment
5	1	87.9	87.9	316.4	382.3	382.3	1376.4
4	1	78.4	166.3	915.3	342.1	724.4	3984.2
3	1	69.1	235.4	1762.8	301.9	1026.3	7679.0
2	1	59.0	294.4	2822.5	258.4	1284.7	12303.9
1	1	49.6	344.0	4060.9	220.4	1505.1	17722.2

Diagram 7-1.1 Sketch of Floor shear under wind load(Tower 1)

Diagram 7.1-2 Sketch of Floor bending moment under wind load(Tower 1)

7.2 The statistical frame shear under wind load

This is shown from table 7.2-1 to table 7.2-2

Table 7.2-1 Frame Column, shear wall in X direction wind shear and percentage (units: kN)

Floor	Tower	Column shear	Wall shear	Total shear	Column shear percentage	Wall shear percentage
5	1	87.9	0.0	87.9	100.00%	0.00%
4	1	166.3	0.0	166.3	100.00%	0.00%
3	1	235.4	0.0	235.4	100.00%	0.00%
2	1	294.4	0.0	294.4	100.00%	0.00%
1	1	344.0	0.0	344.0	100.00%	0.00%

Table 7.2-2 Frame Column, Shear Wall In Y direction Wind Shear and Percentage (units: kN)

Floor	Tower	Column shear	Wall shear	Total shear	Column shear percentage	Wall shear percentage
5	1	382.3	0.0	382.3	100.00%	0.00%
4	1	724.4	0.0	724.4	100.00%	0.00%
3	1	1026.3	0.0	1026.3	100.00%	0.00%
2	1	1284.7	0.0	1284.7	100.00%	0.00%
1	1	1505.1	0.0	1505.1	100.00%	0.00%

7.3 Overturn Bending Moment Statistics of frame under wind load by (seismic code)

This is shown from table 7.3-1 to table 7.3-2.

Table 7.3-1 Frame Column Wind Overturn Moment and Percentage In X direction (units: kN.m)

Floor	Tower	Column moment	Total moment	Column moment percentage
5	1	316.4	316.4	100.00%
4	1	915.3	915.3	100.00%
3	1	1762.8	1762.8	100.00%
2	1	2822.5	2822.5	100.00%
1	1	4060.9	4060.9	100.00%

Table 7.3-2 Frame Column Wind Overturn Moment and Percentage In Y direction (units: kN.m)

Floor	Tower	Column moment	Total moment	Column moment percentage
5	1	1376.4	1376.4	100.00%
4	1	3984.2	3984.2	100.00%
3	1	7679.0	7679.0	100.00%
2	1	12303.9	12303.9	100.00%
1	1	17722.2	17722.2	100.00%

7.4 Floor-F, Floor-V, Floor-M of wind

Floor-F, Floor-V of wind unit: kN

Floor-M unit: kN.m

This is shown from table 7.4-1 to table 7.4-4.

Table 7.4-1 +WX Floor-F, Floor-V, Floor-M of wind

Floor	Tower	Floor-F	Floor-V	Floor-M
5	1	87.9	87.9	316.4
4	1	78.4	166.3	915.3
3	1	69.1	235.4	1762.8
2	1	59.0	294.4	2822.5
1	1	49.6	344.0	4060.9

Table 7.4-2 -WX Floor-F, Floor-V, Floor-M of wind

Floor	Tower	Floor-F	Floor-V	Floor-M
5	1	-87.9	-87.9	-316.4
4	1	-78.4	-166.3	-915.3
3	1	-69.1	-235.4	-1762.8
2	1	-59.0	-294.4	-2822.5
1	1	-49.6	-344.0	-4060.9

Table 7.4-3 +WY Floor-F, Floor-V, Floor-M of wind

Floor	Tower	Floor-F	Floor-V	Floor-M
5	1	382.3	382.3	1376.4
4	1	342.1	724.4	3984.2
3	1	301.9	1026.3	7679.0
2	1	258.4	1284.7	12303.9
1	1	220.4	1505.1	17722.2

Table 7.4-4 -WY Floor-F, Floor-V, Floor-M of wind

Floor	Tower	Floor-F	Floor-V	Floor-M
5	1	-382.3	-382.3	-1376.4
4	1	-342.1	-724.4	-3984.2
3	1	-301.9	-1026.3	-7679.0
2	1	-258.4	-1284.7	-12303.9
1	1	-220.4	-1505.1	-17722.2

7.5 Prescribed horizontal force

This is shown in table 7.5-1.

Table 7.5.1 Prescribed horizontal force of each tower in each floor

Floor	Tower	X Direction(kN)	Y Direction(kN)
5	1	1930.1	1831.1
4	1	1295.8	1059.2
3	1	958.3	755.6
2	1	738.0	642.5
1	1	448.2	434.0

7.6 Overturn Bending Moment Statistics under prescribed Horizontal Force (by seismic code)

This is shown from table 7.6-1 to table 7.6-2.

Table 7-6.1 Seismic overturn bending moment (units:kN.m) and Percentage (by seismic code) of frame columns、 short-limb walls In X direction

Floor	Tower	Frame Columns	Short-Limb Walls	Normal Walls	斜撑	Total
5	1	6948.2(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	6948.2
4	1	18561.4(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	18561.4
3	1	33624.5(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	33624.5
2	1	51344.3(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	51344.3
1	1	70677.5(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	70677.5

Table 7-6.2 Seismic overturn bending moment (units:kN.m) and Percentage (by seismic code) of frame columns、 short-limb walls In Y direction

Floor	Tower	Frame Columns	Short-Limb Walls	Normal Walls	斜撑	Total
5	1	6592.1(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	6592.1
4	1	16997.2(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	16997.2
3	1	30122.5(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	30122.5
2	1	45560.8(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	45560.8
1	1	62561.7(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	62561.7

Diagram 7-6.1 Diagram of Overturning moment under earthquake action X(Tower 1)

Diagram 7-6.2 Diagram of Overturning moment under earthquake action Y(Tower 1)

7.7 Seismic Overturn Bending Moment Statistics under Stipulated Horizontal Force (by axial-force)

This shown from table 7.7-1 to 7.7-2.

Table 7-7.1 Seismic overturn bending moment (units:kN.m) and Percentage (by Axial-force) of frame columns、 short-limb walls In X direction

Floor	Tower	Frame Columns	Short-Limb Walls	Normal Walls	斜撑	Total
5	1	6948.2(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	6948.2
4	1	18561.4(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	18561.4
3	1	33624.5(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	33624.5
2	1	51344.3(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	51344.3
1	1	70677.5(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	70677.5

Table 7-7.2 Seismic overturn bending moment (units:kN.m) and Percentage (by Axial-force) of frame columns、 short-limb walls In Y direction

Floor	Tower	Frame Columns	Short-Limb Walls	Normal Walls	斜撑	Total
5	1	6592.1(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	6592.1
4	1	16997.2(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	16997.2
3	1	30122.5(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	30122.5
2	1	45560.8(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	45560.8
1	1	62561.7(100.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	0.0(0.0%)	62561.7

Diagram 7-7.1 Diagram of Overturning moment under earthquake action X(Tower 1)

Diagram 7-7.2 Diagram of Overturning moment under earthquake action Y(Tower 1)

7.8 The statistical frame shear under earthquake action

Ratio : Column shear percentage

BVRatio : Column shear and divide base shear percentage

This is shown from table 7.8-1 to table 7.8-2.

Table 7-8.1 Seismic Shear in X direction (unit: kN) and percentage

Floor	Tower	Column shear	Wall shear	Total shear	Ratio	BVRatio
5	1	1930.1	0.0	1930.1	100.00%	0.00%
4	1	3225.9	0.0	3225.9	100.00%	0.00%
3	1	4184.2	0.0	4184.2	100.00%	0.00%
2	1	4922.2	0.0	4922.2	100.00%	0.00%
1	1	5370.3	0.0	5370.3	100.00%	0.00%

Diagram 7-8.1 Sketch of Shear In X earthquake action(Tower 1)

Table 7-8.2 Seismic Shear in Y direction (unit: kN) and percentage

Floor	Tower	Column shear	Wall shear	Total shear	Ratio	BVRatio
5	1	1831.1	0.0	1831.1	100.00%	0.00%
4	1	2890.3	0.0	2890.3	100.00%	0.00%
3	1	3645.9	0.0	3645.9	100.00%	0.00%
2	1	4288.4	0.0	4288.4	100.00%	0.00%
1	1	4722.5	0.0	4722.5	100.00%	0.00%

Diagram 7-8.2 Sketch of Shear In Y earthquake action(Tower 1)

7.9 Floor-F, Floor-V, Floor-M of Seismic

Floor-F, Floor-V unit: kN

Floor-M unit: kN.m

This is shown in table 7.9-1.

Table 7.9-1 EX, EY Floor-F, Floor-V, Floor-M of Seismic

Floor	Tower	Floor-FX	Floor-VX	Floor-MX	Floor-FY	Floor-VY	Floor-MY
5	1	1930.1	1930.1	6948.2	1831.1	1831.1	6592.1
4	1	1605.2	3225.9	18245.4	1455.7	2890.3	16612.6
3	1	1520.4	4184.2	32564.7	1450.5	3645.9	28813.5
2	1	1446.4	4922.2	49153.5	1443.9	4288.4	42821.2
1	1	1123.4	5370.3	67268.3	1133.0	4722.5	58313.8

Diagram 7-9.1 Sketch of Floor shear under earthquake action(Tower 1)

CHAPTER 8 LOAD CASE, LOAD COMBINATION

8.1 Load case define

This is shown in table 8.1-1

Table 8.1-1 Load case define

Load case	Explain for short name
EX	EX -- Standard internal force under X earthquake force
EY	EY -- Standard internal force under Y earthquake force
+WX	+WX -- Standard internal force under +X wind load
-WX	-WX -- Standard internal force under -X wind load
+WY	+WY -- Standard internal force under +Y wind load
-WY	-WY -- Standard internal force under -Y wind load
DEAD	DL -- Standard internal force under dead load
LIVE	LL -- Standard internal force under live load
EZ	EV -- Standard internal force under vertical earthquake action

8.2 Load combination table

This is shown in table 8.2-1

Table 8.2-1 Load combination table

LDCombID	Dead load	Live load	Wind +X	Wind -X	Wind +Y	Wind -Y	Seism X	Seism Y	Seism Z	Nonlinear
1	1.30	1.50								linear
2	1.00	1.50								linear
3	1.30		1.50							linear
4	1.30			1.50						linear
5	1.30				1.50					linear
6	1.30					1.50				linear
7	1.30	1.50	0.90							linear
8	1.30	1.50		0.90						linear
9	1.30	1.50			0.90					linear
10	1.30	1.50				0.90				linear
11	1.30	1.05	1.50							linear
12	1.30	1.05		1.50						linear
13	1.30	1.05			1.50					linear
14	1.30	1.05				1.50				linear
15	1.00		1.50							linear
16	1.00			1.50						linear

CHAPTER 8 LOAD CASE, LOAD COMBINATION

LDCombID	Dead load	Live load	Wind +X	Wind -X	Wind +Y	Wind -Y	Seism X	Seism Y	Seism Z	Nonlinear
17	1.00				1.50					linear
18	1.00					1.50				linear
19	1.00	1.50	0.90							linear
20	1.00	1.50		0.90						linear
21	1.00	1.50			0.90					linear
22	1.00	1.50				0.90				linear
23	1.00	1.05	1.50							linear
24	1.00	1.05		1.50						linear
25	1.00	1.05			1.50					linear
26	1.00	1.05				1.50				linear
27	1.30	0.65					1.40			linear
28	1.30	0.65					-1.40			linear
29	1.30	0.65						1.40		linear
30	1.30	0.65						-1.40		linear
31	1.00	0.50					1.40			linear
32	1.00	0.50					-1.40			linear
33	1.00	0.50						1.40		linear
34	1.00	0.50						-1.40		linear
35	1.30	0.65					1.40		0.50	linear
36	1.30	0.65					1.40		-0.50	linear
37	1.30	0.65					-1.40		0.50	linear
38	1.30	0.65					-1.40		-0.50	linear
39	1.30	0.65						1.40	0.50	linear
40	1.30	0.65						1.40	-0.50	linear
41	1.30	0.65						-1.40	0.50	linear
42	1.30	0.65						-1.40	-0.50	linear
43	1.00	0.50					1.40		0.50	linear
44	1.00	0.50					1.40		-0.50	linear
45	1.00	0.50					-1.40		0.50	linear
46	1.00	0.50					-1.40		-0.50	linear
47	1.00	0.50						1.40	0.50	linear
48	1.00	0.50						1.40	-0.50	linear
49	1.00	0.50						-1.40	0.50	linear
50	1.00	0.50						-1.40	-0.50	linear
51	1.30	0.65					0.50		1.40	linear
52	1.30	0.65					0.50		-1.40	linear
53	1.30	0.65					-0.50		1.40	linear
54	1.30	0.65					-0.50		-1.40	linear
55	1.30	0.65						0.50	1.40	linear

CHAPTER 8 LOAD CASE, LOAD COMBINATION

LDCombID	Dead load	Live load	Wind +X	Wind -X	Wind +Y	Wind -Y	Seism X	Seism Y	Seism Z	Nonlinear
56	1.30	0.65						0.50	-1.40	linear
57	1.30	0.65						-0.50	1.40	linear
58	1.30	0.65						-0.50	-1.40	linear
59	1.00	0.50					0.50		1.40	linear
60	1.00	0.50					0.50		-1.40	linear
61	1.00	0.50					-0.50		1.40	linear
62	1.00	0.50					-0.50		-1.40	linear
63	1.00	0.50						0.50	1.40	linear
64	1.00	0.50						0.50	-1.40	linear
65	1.00	0.50						-0.50	1.40	linear
66	1.00	0.50						-0.50	-1.40	linear
67	1.30	0.65							1.40	linear
68	1.30	0.65							-1.40	linear
69	1.00	0.50							1.40	linear
70	1.00	0.50							-1.40	linear

CHAPTER 9 PROJECT QUOTA STAT

9.1 Period ratio

The first torsion period(0.9278)/The first translation period(0.9739) = 0.95

9.2 The floor stiffness statistics (Stiffness-Center of each floor Eccentricity ratio Lateral stiffness ratio of Adjacency-Layers etc calculation information)

Xstif,Ystif(m): Stiffness-Center of coordinate value X、Y

Alf(Degree): The direction of the rigid main axis

Xmass,Ymass(m): Coordinate value X、Y of centroid

Gmass(t): Total mass

Eex,Eey: Eccentricity ratio in X,Y direction

This is shown in table 9.2-1.

Table 9-2.1 Stiffness-Center of each floor Eccentricity ratio Lateral stiffness ratio of Adjacency-Layers etc calculation information.

Floor	Tower	Xstif,Ystif	Alf	Xmass,Ymass	Gmass	Eex,Eey
5	1	36.15,8.26	45.00	36.15,8.26	1881.82	0.00%,0.00%
4	1	36.15,8.25	45.00	36.23,8.37	1981.53	0.53%,0.36%
3	1	36.15,8.25	45.00	36.23,8.37	1981.53	0.53%,0.36%
2	1	36.15,8.25	45.00	36.23,8.37	1981.53	0.53%,0.36%
1	1	36.15,8.25	45.00	35.88,8.35	2055.56	0.46%,1.16%

《Technical specification for concrete structures of tall building》（JGJ 3-2010）
 3.5.2-1: for frame Structure, the ratio of lateral stiffness between the floor and the adjacent upper floor should not be less than 0.7, and the Ratio of Lateral Stiffness of the Floor to the average Lateral Stiffness of the adjacent upper three floors should not be less than 0.8.

《Technical specification for concrete structures of tall building》（JGJ 3-2010）
 3.5.2-1: for Frame-Shear Wall Structure, Slab-Column-Wall Structure, Shear Wall Structure, Frame-Core Wall Structure, Tube in Tube Structure, the ratio γ_2 of lateral stiffness between the floor and the adjacent upper floor can be calculated according to the formula (3.5.2-2) , and it should not be less than 0.9; When the layer is 1.5 times higher than the adjacent upper layer, the ratio should not be less than 1.1; For the Bottom embedded floor, the ratio should not be less than 1.5.

Ratx,Raty: The ratio of the layer tower lateral stiffness and the next layer corresponding tower lateral stiffness in X,Y direction

Ratx1,Raty1: The smaller one of the ratio of lateral stiffness of this layer tower and 70% of that of corresponding tower of the upper layer or 80%

of average lateral stiffness of three upper layers in X,Y direction

Ratx2,Raty2: The ratio of lateral stiffness of this layer tower in X,Y direction and 90% ,110%,or 150% of that of corresponding tower of the upper layer. 110% indicates that the height of this layer is taller than 1.5 times of the height of the upper adjacent layer. 150% is fixed floors.

RJX1,RJY1,RJZ1: The tower lateral stiffness and torsional stiffness in the overall structure coordinate system (shear-cut stiffness)

RJX3,RJY3,RJZ3: The lateral stiffness and torsional stiffness of the tower in the overall structure coordinate system (Seismic shear force and The ratio of seismic layer displacement)

Rs: Weak layer seismic sheat amplification coefficient

This is shown in table 9.2-2.

Table 9.2-2

Floor	Tower	Ratx,Raty	Ratx1,Raty1	RJX1,RJY1 (kN/m)	RJX3,RJY3 (kN/m)	Rs
5	1	1.00,1.00	1.00,1.00	5.63E+006 5.63E+006	1.03E+006 6.76E+005	1.00
4	1	1.00,1.00	1.52,1.62	5.63E+006 5.63E+006	1.09E+006 7.68E+005	1.00
3	1	1.00,1.00	1.30,1.40	5.63E+006 5.63E+006	1.11E+006 8.08E+005	1.00
2	1	1.00,1.00	1.41,1.56	5.63E+006 5.63E+006	1.21E+006 9.36E+005	1.00
1	1	1.00,1.00	2.34,2.66	5.63E+006 5.63E+006	2.13E+006 1.78E+006	1.00

Minimum stiffness ratio in X direction: 1.0000(5 Floor 1 Tower)

Minimum stiffness ratio in Y direction: 1.0000(5 Floor 1 Tower)

Diagram 9.2-1 Multi-dir Stiffness Ratio diagram(Tower 1)

Diagram 9.2-2 Multi-dir Stiffness Ratio diagram(Tower 1)

9.3 Checking calculation for structure whole stability

Stiffness unit: kN/m

Floor height unit: m

Mass-Above unit: kN

This is shown in table 9.3-1.

Table 9.3-1 Earthquake

Floor	Tower	Stiffness X	Stiffness Y	Floor height	Mass-Above	Rigidity/gravity-X	Rigidity/gravity-Y
1	1	2.128E+006	1.782E+006	3.600	134494	5.695E+001	4.769E+001
2	1	1.212E+006	9.362E+005	3.600	106252	4.108E+001	3.172E+001
3	1	1.106E+006	8.083E+005	3.600	80042	4.973E+001	3.636E+001
4	1	1.094E+006	7.684E+005	3.600	53831	7.315E+001	5.139E+001
5	1	1.029E+006	6.764E+005	3.600	27621	1.341E+002	8.816E+001

The ratio of rigidity-to-gravity of the structure $D_i \cdot H_i / G_i$ is bigger than 10, satisfying the overall stability checking calculation in Code 5.4.4

The ratio of rigidity-to-gravity of the structure $D_i \cdot H_i / G_i$ is bigger than 20, satisfying Code 5.4.1, gravity second-order effect can be left out

9.4 Checking calculation for the overturn resistance of the whole structure

According to 《Technical specification for concrete structures of tall building》 (JGJ 3-2010) 12.1.7, Under the action of gravity load and Horizontal load standard value or gravity load representative value and the frequently occurred horizontal earthquake standard value, zero stress zone should not appear in the bottom of foundation for tall building with the depth-width ratio greater than 4; The area of zero stress should not exceed 15% of the basal area for tall building with the depth-width ratio less than 4. The checking Calculation result for the Overturn Resistance of the Whole Structure is as follows in table 9.4-1:

Table 9.4-1 Checking Calculation for the Overturn Resistance of the Whole Structure (units: kN.m)

Floor	Tower	Case	Anti-Overturn Mr	Overturn Mov	Ratio Mr/Mov	Zero stressed zone(%)
1	1	Wind X	3.700E+006	4.128E+003	896.37	0.00
		Wind Y	8.239E+005	1.806E+004	45.62	0.00
		Seism X	3.557E+006	6.444E+004	55.19	0.00
		Seism Y	7.920E+005	5.667E+004	13.98	0.00

9.5 Checking calculation for floor shear resistance load-bearing capacity

《Technical specification for concrete structures of tall building》 (JGJ 3-2010)
 3.5.3, For tall building of Class A height, The layer shear capacity of Lateral force resisting structure cannot be less than 80% of that of the adjacent upper floor, and should not be less than 65% of that of the adjacent upper floor; For tall building of Class B height, The layer shear capacity of Lateral force resisting structure should not be less than 75% of that of the adjacent upper floor

The limit value set for the structure is 80%. There is no mutation in the bearing capacity of the floor.

Ratio_X,Ratio_Y: Indicating the ratio of Load-bearing capacity of this floor and the upper floor

This is shown in table 9.51.

Table 9.5-1 Checking Calculation for Floor Shear Resistance Load-Bearing Capacity (units:kN)

Floor	Tower	Load-bearing X	Load-bearing Y	Ratio_X	Ratio_Y
5	1	1.3663E+004	1.4406E+004	1.00	1.00
4	1	1.6978E+004	1.7526E+004	1.24	1.22
3	1	2.0018E+004	2.0664E+004	1.18	1.18
2	1	2.2782E+004	2.3517E+004	1.14	1.14
1	1	2.5358E+004	2.7851E+004	1.11	1.18

Diagram 9.5-1 Diagram of Multi-dir Shear Resistance Load-Bearing Capacity ratio(Tower 1)

9.6 Weak-floor information

This is shown in table 9.6-1

Table 9.6-1 Weak-floor

Floor	Tower
-------	-------

9.7 Adjustment coefficient of the shear-weight ratio

This is shown in table 9.7-1.

Table 9.7-1 The adjustment of seismic shear force coefficient of each floor[checking calculation of Seismic Code (5.2.5)]

Floor	Tower	Adjustment X	Adjustment Y	Adjusted VX	Adjusted VY
5	1	1.00	1.00	1930.06	1831.14
4	1	1.00	1.00	3225.88	2890.30
3	1	1.00	1.00	4184.18	3645.93
2	1	1.00	1.00	4922.18	4288.42
1	1	1.00	1.00	5370.34	4722.46

9.8 Dis-angle and Displacement ratio

According to 《Technical specification for concrete structures of tall building》 (JGJ 3-2010) 3.7.3, The limit values of Inter-story Maximum Displacement and floor height ratio are shown in the following table 9.8-1:

Table 9.8-1 The limit values of Inter-story Maximum Displacement and floor height ratio [Height Code(3.7.3)]

Type of structure	$\Delta u/h$ limit value
Frame	1/550
Frame-Shear Wall,Frame-Core Wall,Slab-Column-Wall	1/800
Tube in Tube,Shear Wall	1/1000
The transformation layer except Frame Structure	1/1000

《Code for seismic design of buildings》 (GB 50011-2010) 3.4.3-1, torsional irregularity is defined as: Under the action of stipulated horizontal force, floors 'maximum elastic horizontal displacement (or Inter-story Displacement) is greater than 1.2 times average displacement of two ends of the floor(or Inter-story Displacement). According to 《Technical specification for concrete structures of tall building》 (JGJ 3-2010) 3.4.5, Under the action of stipulated horizontal earthquake force Considering the effect of accidental eccentric, For tall building of Class A height, The maximum horizontal displacement and Inter-story Displacement of vertical floor member cannot be greater than 1.2 times the average of the floor, and should not be greater than 1.5 times the average; For tall building of Class B height, Mixed structures higher than Class A height and Complicated Tall Buildings, it cannot be greater than 1.2 times the average of the floor, and should not be greater than 1.4times the average. The displacement ratio which is Judging torsional Irregularity set for the structure is 1.2.The limit value is 1.5.

The calculation results of force rigid floor assumption mode

- Unit: mm
 - h: Floor height
 - Max-(X), Max-(Y): Max nodal points disp. in X,Y direction
 - Ave-(X), Ave-(Y): Floor average displacement in X,Y direction
 - Max-Dx , Max-Dy: Max disp. between floors in X,Y direction
 - Ave-Dx , Ave-Dy: Average disp. between floors in X,Y direction
 - Ratio-(X),Ratio-(Y): The ratio of Max displacement and floor average displacement
 - Ratio-Dx, Ratio-Dy: The ratio of Max floor displacement and average floor displacement
 - Max-Dx/h, Max-Dy/h: Max storey drift angles in X,Y direction
- This is shown from table 9.8-2 to table 9.8-9.

Table 9.8-2 Maximum floor displacement under earthquake action X

Floor	Tower	Max-(X)	Ave-(X)	Max-Dx	Ave-Dx	Max-Dx/h	h
5	1	14.86	14.81	1.88	1.88	1/1912	3600.00
4	1	13.14	13.10	2.96	2.95	1/1216	3600.00
3	1	10.32	10.29	3.80	3.78	1/948	3600.00
2	1	6.59	6.57	4.07	4.06	1/884	3600.00
1	1	2.53	2.52	2.53	2.52	1/1423	3600.00

Max floor drift angle in X direction: 1/884 (2 Floor 1 Tower)

Table 9.8-3 Maximum floor displacement under earthquake action Y

Floor	Tower	Max-(Y)	Ave-(Y)	Max-Dy	Ave-Dy	Max-Dy/h	h
5	1	17.82	17.69	2.72	2.71	1/1324	3600.00
4	1	15.32	15.21	3.78	3.76	1/951	3600.00
3	1	11.72	11.64	4.54	4.51	1/792	3600.00
2	1	7.27	7.21	4.62	4.58	1/780	3600.00
1	1	2.67	2.65	2.67	2.65	1/1349	3600.00

Max floor drift angle in Y direction: 1/780 (2 Floor 1 Tower)

Table 9.8-4 Maximum floor displacement under wind +X

Floor	Tower	Max-(X)	Ave-(X)	Ratio-(X)	Max-Dx	Ave-Dx	Ratio-Dx	Max-Dx/h	h
5	1	0.88	0.88	1.00	0.10	0.10	1.00	1/9999	3600.00
4	1	0.79	0.78	1.00	0.16	0.16	1.00	1/9999	3600.00
3	1	0.63	0.62	1.00	0.22	0.22	1.00	1/9999	3600.00
2	1	0.41	0.40	1.00	0.25	0.25	1.00	1/9999	3600.00
1	1	0.16	0.16	1.00	0.16	0.16	1.00	1/9999	3600.00

Max floor drift angle in X direction: 1/9999 (2 Floor 1 Tower)

The ratio of maximum displacement and floor average displacement in the X direction:
1.00 (3 Floor 1 Tower)

The ratio of maximum displacement and average displacement between floors in the X
direction: 1.00 (5 Floor 1 Tower)

Table 9.8-5 Maximum floor displacement under wind -X

Floor	Tower	Max-(X)	Ave-(X)	Ratio-(X)	Max-Dx	Ave-Dx	Ratio-Dx	Max-Dx/h	h
5	1	0.88	0.88	1.00	0.10	0.10	1.00	1/9999	3600.00
4	1	0.79	0.78	1.00	0.16	0.16	1.00	1/9999	3600.00
3	1	0.63	0.62	1.00	0.22	0.22	1.00	1/9999	3600.00
2	1	0.41	0.40	1.00	0.25	0.25	1.00	1/9999	3600.00
1	1	0.16	0.16	1.00	0.16	0.16	1.00	1/9999	3600.00

Max floor drift angle in X direction: 1/9999 (2 Floor 1 Tower)

The ratio of maximum displacement and floor average displacement in the X direction:
1.00 (3 Floor 1 Tower)

The ratio of maximum displacement and average displacement between floors in the X
direction: 1.00 (5 Floor 1 Tower)

Table 9.8-6 Maximum floor displacement under wind +Y

Floor	Tower	Max-(Y)	Ave-(Y)	Ratio-(Y)	Max-Dy	Ave-Dy	Ratio-Dy	Max-Dy/h	h
5	1	5.25	5.25	1.00	0.69	0.69	1.00	1/5239	3600.00
4	1	4.56	4.56	1.00	1.02	1.02	1.00	1/3517	3600.00
3	1	3.54	3.54	1.00	1.31	1.31	1.00	1/2740	3600.00
2	1	2.23	2.23	1.00	1.40	1.40	1.00	1/2574	3600.00
1	1	0.83	0.83	1.00	0.83	0.83	1.00	1/4324	3600.00

Max floor drift angle in Y direction: 1/2574 (2 Floor 1 Tower)

The ratio of maximum displacement and floor average displacement in the Y direction:
1.00 (1 Floor 1 Tower)

The ratio of maximum displacement and average displacement between floors in the Y direction: 1.00 (1 Floor 1 Tower)

Table 9.8-7 Maximum floor displacement under wind -Y

Floor	Tower	Max-(Y)	Ave-(Y)	Ratio-(Y)	Max-Dy	Ave-Dy	Ratio-Dy	Max-Dy/h	h
5	1	5.25	5.25	1.00	0.69	0.69	1.00	1/5239	3600.00
4	1	4.56	4.56	1.00	1.02	1.02	1.00	1/3517	3600.00
3	1	3.54	3.54	1.00	1.31	1.31	1.00	1/2740	3600.00
2	1	2.23	2.23	1.00	1.40	1.40	1.00	1/2574	3600.00
1	1	0.83	0.83	1.00	0.83	0.83	1.00	1/4324	3600.00

Max floor drift angle in Y direction: 1/2574 (2 Floor 1 Tower)

The ratio of maximum displacement and floor average displacement in the Y direction:
1.00 (1 Floor 1 Tower)

The ratio of maximum displacement and average displacement between floors in the Y direction: 1.00 (1 Floor 1 Tower)

Table 9.8-8 Maximum floor displacement under stipulated horizontal force X

Floor	Tower	Max-(X)	Ave-(X)	Ratio-(X)	Max-Dx	Ave-Dx	Ratio-Dx	h
5	1	15.54	15.52	1.00	1.94	1.94	1.00	3600.00
4	1	13.60	13.59	1.00	3.04	3.04	1.00	3600.00
3	1	10.56	10.55	1.00	3.88	3.87	1.00	3600.00
2	1	6.68	6.67	1.00	4.13	4.12	1.00	3600.00
1	1	2.55	2.55	1.00	2.55	2.55	1.00	3600.00

The ratio of maximum displacement and floor average displacement in the X direction:
1.00 (3 Floor 1 Tower)

The ratio of maximum displacement and average displacement between floors in the X direction: 1.00 (2 Floor 1 Tower)

Table 9.8-9 Maximum floor displacement under stipulated horizontal force Y

Floor	Tower	Max-(Y)	Ave-(Y)	Ratio-(Y)	Max-Dy	Ave-Dy	Ratio-Dy	h
5	1	18.98	18.94	1.00	2.87	2.87	1.00	3600.00
4	1	16.11	16.07	1.00	3.96	3.95	1.00	3600.00
3	1	12.15	12.12	1.00	4.71	4.70	1.00	3600.00
2	1	7.44	7.42	1.00	4.73	4.72	1.00	3600.00
1	1	2.71	2.70	1.00	2.71	2.70	1.00	3600.00

The ratio of maximum displacement and floor average displacement in the Y direction:
1.00 (2 Floor 1 Tower)

The ratio of maximum displacement and average displacement between floors in the Y direction: 1.00 (2 Floor 1 Tower)

Diagram 9.8-1 Max Floor displacement ratio diagram under the Prescribed horizontal force action(Tower 1)

Diagram 9.8-2 Floor-inter displacement ratio diagram under the Prescribed horizontal force action(Tower 1)

Diagram 9.8-3 Sketch of Max floor displacement(Tower 1)

Diagram 9.8-4 Sketch of Max storey drift angles(Tower 1)

9.9 Checking Calculation of Human comfortableness of Wind vibration

According to 《Technical specification for concrete structures of tall building》 (JGJ 3-2010) 3.7.6, Should meet the requirements of Human Comfortableness of Wind .Under the action of the 10-year return period nominal Wind load value, The maximum acceleration calculated value of the structure apex under following wind and cross-wind Vibration should not exceed 0.15 m/s² for residential apartments, and should not exceed 0.25 m/s² for offices and hotels.

《Technical specification for steel structure of tall building》 (JGJ99-2015) 3.5.5, steel structure of tall building which is not less than 150m Under the action of the 10-year return period nominal Wind load value, The maximum acceleration calculated value of the structure apex under following wind and cross-wind Vibration should not exceed 0.2 m/s² for residential apartments, and should not exceed 0.28 m/s² for offices and hotels.

The specific method of calculation refer to appendix J of 《Load code》 . This is shown in table 9.9-1.

Table 9.9-1 Max accelerated speed of top end

Tower	Calculating with Load Code for the Design of Building Structures, Appendix J
1	Along-wind in the direction of X(m/s ²)= 0.013 Across-wind in the direction of X(m/s ²)= 0.005 long-wind in the direction of Y(m/s ²)= 0.053 Across-wind in the direction of Y(m/s ²)= 0.943

CHAPTER 10 STEEL BAR REINFORCEMENT

10.1 Slab steel bar of standard floor

Negative rib number diagram table (1) layer

Numbering	Shape and size	specification
①		Φ10@200
②		Φ10@200
③		Φ12@150
④		Φ10@200
⑤		Φ10@150
⑥		Φ16@200
⑦		Φ12@200
⑧		Φ10@200
⑨		Φ10@150
⑩		Φ10@200
⑪		Φ10@200

Diagram 10.1-1 Negative rib number diagram table

Positive rib number diagram table (1) layer

numbering	Board thickness	Solid reinforcement	Reinforcement schematic
LB1	100	B: X Φ10@150, Y Φ10@200	
LB2	100	B: X Φ10@200, Y Φ10@200	
LB3	100	B: X Φ12@200, Y Φ10@200	

Diagram 10.1-2 Positive rib number diagram table

10.2 Slab steel bar of fifth floor

Negative rib numbering diagram table (5) layer

numbering	Shape and size	specification
①		Φ10@200
②		Φ10@200
③		Φ16@200
④		Φ10@200
⑤		Φ10@100
⑥		Φ10@200
⑦		Φ10@150
⑧		Φ10@200

Diagram 10.2-1 Negative rib number diagram table

Positive rib number diagram table (5) layer

numbering	Board thickness	Solid reinforcement	Reinforcement schematic
WB1	100	B: X Φ12@200, Y Φ10@200	
WB2	100	B: X Φ10@200, Y Φ10@200	
WB3	100	B: X Φ10@150, Y Φ10@200	

Diagram 10.2-1 Negative rib number diagram table

10.3 Beam steel bar of standard floor

Beam table

Analysis	Cross-number	Beam logs Elevation difference	Beam section b×h	Span 1		Span 2		Span 3		Stirrups	Reinforcement
				Span 1	Span 2	Span 1	Span 2	Span 1	Span 2		
KL1(3)	1		300x500	222+218	222	422	222+118(-1)		G412	8@100/200(2)	
	2		300x500	422	422	422	320		G412	8@100(2)	
	3		300x500	422	222	422	225+122(-1)		G412	8@100/200(2)	
KL2(16)	1		400x600	616	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	2		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	3		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	4		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	5		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	6		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	7		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	8		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	9		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	10		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	11		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	12		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	13		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	14		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	15		400x600	516	416	516	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	16		400x600	516	416	616	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	

Diagram 10.3-1 Beam table

10.4 Beam steel bar of fifth floor

Beam table

Analysis	Cross-number	Beam logs Elevation difference	Beam section b×h	Span 1		Span 2		Span 3		Stirrups	Reinforcement
				Span 1	Span 2	Span 1	Span 2	Span 1	Span 2		
WKL1(3)	1		300x500	516	216	516	220+118(-1)		G412	8@100/200(2)	
	2		300x500	316	316	316	314		G412	8@100(2)	
	3		300x500	516	216	516	220+118(-1)		G412	8@100/200(2)	
WKL2(16)	1		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	2		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	3		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	4		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	5		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	6		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	7		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	8		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	9		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	10		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	11		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	12		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	13		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	14		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	15		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	
	16		400x600	514	214+(28)	514	416		G412	8@100/200(4)	

Diagram 10.4-1 Beam table

10.5 Column steel bar of all floors

Bars

Column number	Elevation	b×h (Cylinder diameter D)	b ₁	b ₂	h ₁	h ₂	All longitudinal ribs	Horn tendons	Side B Middle tendon	H-side side Middle tendon	Stirrups Type number	Stirrups	Notes
KZ1	0.000~18.000	600×600	300	300	300	300		4Φ20	2Φ18	2Φ16	1(4×4)	Φ8@100/150	

Stirrup type 1(m×n)

Diagram 10.5-1 Bar table

CHAPTER 11 SKETCH OF STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND DESIGN RESULTS

11.1 Sketch of structural plane

The 1 Floor (Standard floor) sketch of element is

Diagram 11.1-1 1 Floor Sketch of layer structural plane

The 2 Floor (Standard floor) sketch of element is

Diagram 11.1-2 2 Floor Sketch of layer structural plane

The 3 Floor (Standard floor) sketch of element is

Diagram 11.1-3 3 Floor Sketch of layer structural plane

The 4 Floor (Standard floor2) sketch of element list

Diagram 11.1-4 4 Floor Sketch of layer structural plane

The 5 Floor (Standard floor3) sketch of element list

Diagram 11.1-5 5 Floor Sketch of layer structural plane

11.2 Sketch of plane load

Diagram 11.2-1 1 Floor Sketch of layer plane load

Diagram 11.2-2 2 Floor Sketch of layer plane load

Diagram 11.2-3 3 Floor Sketch of layer plane load

Diagram 11.2-4 4 Floor Sketch of layer plane load

Diagram 11.2-5 5 Floor Sketch of layer plane load

11.3 Sketch of vertical load

Diagram 11.3-1 1 Floor Sketch of layer vertical load

Diagram 11.3-2 2 Floor Sketch of layer vertical load

Diagram 11.3-3 3 Floor Sketch of layer vertical load

Diagram 11.3-4 4 Floor Sketch of layer vertical load

Diagram 11.3-5 5 Floor Sketch of layer vertical load

11.4 Sketch of slab load

Diagram 11.4-1 1 Floor Sketch of layer slab load

Diagram 11.4-2 2 Floor Sketch of layer slab load

Diagram 11.4-3 3 Floor Sketch of layer slab load

Diagram 11.4-4 4 Floor Sketch of layer slab load

Diagram 11.4-5 5 Floor Sketch of layer slab load

11.5 Sketch of slab thickness

Diagram 11.5-1 1 Floor Sketch of layer slab thickness

Diagram 11.5-2 2 Floor Sketch of layer slab thickness

Diagram 11.5-3 3 Floor Sketch of layer slab thickness

Diagram 11.5-4 4 Floor Sketch of layer slab thickness

Diagram 11.5-5 5 Floor Sketch of layer slab thickness

11.6 Sketch of reinforcement

The 1 Floor (Standard floor) sketch of element reinforcement or stress ratio (unit:cm²)
 Floor height=3000(mm) Beam num=115 Column num=68
 Concrete grade: Beam=C30 Column=C30
 Main bar strength: Beam=HRB300 Column=HRB300
 Hoop bar (distribution bar) strength: Beam=HRB300 Column=HRB300
 Stirrup Space(mm): Beam=100 Column=100

Diagram 11.6-1 1 Floor Sketch of layer reinforcement

The 2 Floor (Standard floor) sketch of element reinforcement or stress ratio (unit:cm²)
 Floor height=3000(mm) Beam num=115 Column num=68
 Concrete grade: Beam=C30 Column=C30
 Main bar strength: Beam=HRB300 Column=HRB300
 Hoop bar (distribution bar) strength: Beam=HRB300 Column=HRB300
 Stirrup Space(mm): Beam=100 Column=100

Diagram 11.6-2 2 Floor Sketch of layer reinforcement

The 3 Floor (Standard floor) sketch of element reinforcement or stress ratio(Unit:cm²)
 Floor height=3600(mm) Beam num=115 Column num=48
 Concrete grade: Beam=C30 Column=C40
 Mesh bar strength: Beam=HRB300 Column=HRB400
 Hook bar (distribution bar) strength: Beam=360 Column=360
 Stirrup Space(mm): Beam=100 Column=100

Diagram 11.6-3 3 Floor Sketch of layer reinforcement

The 4 Floor (Standard floor) sketch of element reinforcement or stress ratio(Unit:cm²)
 Floor height=3600(mm) Beam num=115 Column num=48
 Concrete grade: Beam=C30 Column=C40
 Mesh bar strength: Beam=HRB300 Column=HRB400
 Hook bar (distribution bar) strength: Beam=360 Column=360
 Stirrup Space(mm): Beam=100 Column=100

Diagram 11.6-4 4 Floor Sketch of layer reinforcement

The 5 Floor (Standard floor) sketch of element reinforcement or stress ratio(Unit:cm²)
 Floor height=3600(mm) Beam num=115 Column num=48
 Concrete grade: Beam=C30 Column=C40
 Mesh bar strength: Beam=HRB300 Column=HRB400
 Hook bar (distribution bar) strength: Beam=360 Column=360
 Stirrup Space(mm): Beam=100 Column=100

Diagram 11.6-5 5 Floor Sketch of layer reinforcement

11.7 Sketch of edge reinforcement

The 1 Floor (Standard floor1) sketch of Edge reinforcement

Diagram 11.7-1 1 Floor Sketch of layer Edge reinforcement

The 2 Floor (Standard floor2) sketch of Edge reinforcement

Diagram 11.7-2 2 Floor Sketch of layer Edge reinforcement

The 3 Floor (Standard floor2) sketch of Edge reinforcement

Diagram 11.7-3 3 Floor Sketch of layer Edge reinforcement

The 4 Floor (Standard floor2) sketch of Edge reinforcement

Diagram 11.7-4 4 Floor Sketch of layer Edge reinforcement

The 5 Floor(Standard floor3) sketch of Edge reinforcement

Diagram 11.7-5 5 Floor Sketch of layer Edge reinforcement

11.8 Sketch of Column or wall axial compression ratio

The 1 Floor(Standard floor1) sketch of Wall axial compression ratio

Diagram 11.8-1 1 Floor Sketch of layer Column or Wall axial compression ratio

The 2 Floor(Standard floor2) sketch of Wall axial compression ratio

Diagram 11.8-2 2 Floor Sketch of layer Column or Wall axial compression ratio

The 3 Floor(Standard floor3) sketch of Wall axial compression ratio

Diagram 11.8-3 3 Floor Sketch of layer Column or Wall axial compression ratio

The 4 Floor(Standard floor2) sketch of Net combined axial compression ratio

Diagram 11.8-4 4 Floor Sketch of layer Column or Wall axial compression ratio

The 5 Floor(Standard floor3) sketch of Net combined axial compression ratio

Diagram 11.8-5 5 Floor Sketch of layer Column or Wall axial compression ratio

DESIGN BASIS/REFERENCE

The project is designed according to the following specifications and codes:

- 1、《General code for engineering structures》 GB 55001-2021
- 2、《General code for seismic precaution of buildings and municipal engineering》 GB 55002-2021
- 3、《General code for foundation engineering of building and municipal projects》 GB 55003-2021
- 4、《General code for composite structures》 GB 55004-2021
- 5、《General code for steel structures》 GB 55006-2021
- 6、《General code for masonry structures》 GB 55007-2021
- 7、《General code for concrete structures》 GB 55008-2021
- 8、《General code for assessment and rehabilitation of existing buildings》 GB 55021-2021
- 9、《Load Code》：《Load code for the design of building structures》 GB 50009-2012
- 10、《Concrete Code》：《Code for design of concrete structures》 GB 50010-2010(2015)
- 11、《Seismic Code》：《Code for seismic design of buildings》 GB 50011-2010(2016)
- 12、《High Code》：《Technical Specification for concrete structures of tall building》 JGJ 3-2010
- 13、《Guangdong high code》：Guangdong standard 《Technical specification for concrete structures of tall buildings》 DBJ/T 15-92-2021
- 14、《Shanghai Seismic Code》：Code for engineering design of Shanghai 《Code for seismic design of buildings》 DGJ 08-9-2013
- 15、《Civil air defence Code》：《Code for design of civil air defence basement》 GB 50038-2005
- 16、《Steel Standard》：《Standard for design of steel structures》 GB 50017-2017
- 17、《High Steel Code》：《Technical specification for steel structure of tall building》 JGJ 99-2015
- 18、《Gabled frame Specification》：《Technical specification for steel structure of light-weight Building with gabled frame》 GB51022-2015
- 19、《Cold-formed thin-wall steel Code》：《Technical code of cold-formed thin-wall steel structures》 GB 50018-2002
- 20、《Specially shaped columns Specification》：《Technical specification for concrete structures with specially shaped columns》 JGJ 149-2017
- 21、《Composite structures Code》：《Code for design of composite structures》 JGJ 138-2016
- 22、《Steel-reinforced concrete Specification》：《Technical specification of steel-reinforced concrete structures》 YB 9082-2006
- 23、《Steel tubular Code》：《Technical code for concrete filled steel tubular structures》 GB 50936-2014
- 24、《Steel tube-reinforced concrete column Specification》：《Technical specification for steel tube-reinforced concrete column structures》 T/CECS 188-2019
- 25、《Concrete-filled rectangular steel tube specification》：《Technical specification for structures with concrete-filled rectangular steel tube members》 CECS 159 : 2004

- 26、《Hollow floor Specification》：《Technical specification for cast-in-situ concrete hollow floor structure》CECS 175 : 2004
- 27、《Appraisal Standard》：《Standard for seismic appraisal of buildings 》GB 50023-2009
- 28、《Strengthening Code》：《Design code for strengthening concrete structure》GB 50367-2013
- 29、《Seismic strengthening Specification》：《Technical specification for seismic strengthening of buildings》JGJ 116-2009